

Letter attached to Gerald Avery
Wainwright Fund report.

Ollaberry
Grimms Hill,
Great Missenden,
Bucks,
5/12/71.

Your Ref: AM/16

Miss. J. Nicholson,

The Gerald Avery Wainwright Near Eastern Archaeological Fund,

The University Registry,

Clarendon Building,

Broad Street,

Oxford, OX1 3BD.

Dear Miss Nicholson,

Your letter of 23 June was received by my Father in England and handed to me when I recently returned from Iran. The copy sent to Iran was probably misdirected from Teheran since I have not received it yet.

My grant from the Gerald Avery Wainwright Near Eastern Archaeological Fund was as I am sure you will remember for a period of fifteen months terminating in October 1971, so writing now I am able to present a report on the whole period during which I held the grant.

I am grateful to the Board of Management of the Fund for their support and would appreciate your placing the enclosed report before the Board of Management when they meet shortly. I would be happy to provide the Board any further information they may require.

Yours sincerely,

A.G. Williamson